

PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The concept of "principles" in pedagogy is understood as the most important and essential provisions that reflect the laws of education. They direct the activities of the teacher to the intended goal with less effort and time.

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pedagogical control presupposes, comprehensive and harmonious development, integrated approach, physical culture, pedagogical control, long-term results.

In the theory and practice of physical education, there are various groups and types of principles: general principles of the system of physical education, methodological principles, principles expressing the specifics of certain types of physical education (for example, sports training). They are interconnected and constitute a single system of principles. In my abstract, only the general principles of physical education will be considered. These include:

1. The principle of comprehensive and harmonious development of the individual;
2. The principle of linking physical education with the practice of life;
3. The principle of health-improving orientation of physical education.[4,123]

The principle of comprehensive and harmonious development of the individual. Any person should strive to become useful to his country and society. But this can only be done by people with comprehensively developed spiritual and physical powers.

But they can become such only under the influence of certain social conditions of life, among which a special role belongs to physical education.

The all-round development of the personality reflects the biological regularity, the need for the harmonious development of the systems and organs of a person who, both in social terms and in its biological characteristics, is always a single social personality everywhere.

All this determines the multifaceted nature of the influences on a person in the process of physical education and predetermines the organic connection between various types of education, which should be taken into account and purposefully used in all cases of physical education.[2,56]

The principle of comprehensive and harmonious development of the personality is revealed in two main provisions:

1. Ensuring the unity of all aspects of education that form a harmoniously

developed personality. In the process of physical education and related forms of using physical culture, an integrated approach is needed in solving the problems of moral, aesthetic, physical, mental and labor education. Only in this case are highly developed physical qualities and skills of a person, his record achievements in sports, social value and deep content;

2). Providing broad general physical fitness. The complex use of physical culture factors is necessary for the full general development of vital physical qualities inherent in a person (and motor abilities based on them), along with the formation of a wide fund of motor skills and abilities necessary in life. In accordance with this, in specialized forms of physical education, it is necessary to ensure the unity of general and special physical training.[6,95]

The spiritual world of a person is formed under the influence of the external and, first of all, the social environment, as well

as thanks to the active actions of a person aimed at changing the environment and himself

In the process of physical education - due to the physical and spiritual development of a person - there are huge opportunities for the implementation of the tasks of mental, moral and aesthetic education. The principle of comprehensive and harmonious personal development includes the following basic requirements:

1. strictly observe the unity of the various aspects of education

2. to provide broad general physical fitness[3,87]

The requirements of general physical fitness are based on one of the main laws of human development - the inextricable relationship of systems and organs. Comprehensive physical training is an indispensable basis for any type of activity, serves as an inexhaustible source of moral and physical strength of a person.

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